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Abstract

Since the 1980s there has been an exponential growth in marble demand that has made its exploitation, extraction and conversion into other forms a model for successful economic development on an international scale. However, this sector has reported a detrimental impact on

the environment created by low productivity levels, elevated levels of raw material waste and the procedures it uses to remove and replace dimension stone. An analysis of the environmental, social and cultural aspects of the industry from the perspective of their sustainability potential has been presented over the last decade. The findings show the production of pollutants, their discharge into water bodies, dust emission from cutting operations, the presence of occupational hazards, the development of environmental noise and damage to health in Palestine. Similar situations have been reported in the marble industry in Turkey, corrective actions have been proposed in the marble industry to reduce the damage to workers' health and the environment as well as to strengthen the economic aspects. In this industrial context, actions towards sustainability need to be part of the corporate strategy of the industrial sector. The corporate strategy of the industrial sector should have the aims of improving the quality of life, reducing and eradicating poverty and minimizing the environmental impact of this sector. In the 2020 International Resources Panel, the management of mineral resources in the 21st century, guidance publication for a sustainable development of the mining industry, recommendations were made to improve the economic situation of the mining industry, and environmental standards were set to build trust among companies and the public, and to avoid social conflicts . This article focuses on orienting the mining industry towards a sustainable development until 2022 in the light of the current situation in Turkey with the example of Iscehisar.

Keywords: *Marble in Turkey, Comparison of Marble Potentials of the World and Turkey, Comparison of Turkish Marble Industries, Iscehisar Marbles, Comparison of Turkey and Iscehisar Marbles*

1. Introduction

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development encourages the development of action plans with the goals of ending global poverty, protecting the environment and minimizing the environment. The impacts of climate change are one of the 17 targets set in Target 9, 2030 Agenda titled

"Industry, Innovation and Infrastructures". This goal refers to the generation and implementation of actions to make the industry more efficient and at the same time significantly reduce the amount of waste and carbon dioxide emissions produced in its processes. The method proposed by the Business Council for Sustainable Development (BS) (2002) forms the basis of this research. It consists of a diagnostic study of the context and challenges faced by the Mexican marble industry in the social, political, economic, cultural, environmental, research and development dimensions. As a result of these actions, the productivity of the marble process has improved by 7%. In this context, it is proposed to develop a method that lays the groundwork for setting up a cleaner production scheme for the assessment of air, soil and water pollution problems resulting from stone and marble activities in China . These problems arise from activities. It ¹is indispensable for governments to synergize the strengths of business, school and society in order to transform the marble industry sector in accordance with the following sustainability principles . The integration of the strengths of the marble industry in the international arena under a comprehensive management approach consisting of three helices (government, business and school) allows to align internationally reported experience and knowledge of marble industry processes with local experience. (“Sustainability | Free Full-Text | A Triple-Helix Intervention Approach ...”)

2. A Three Helix Comprehensive Management Approach

Integrating the strengths of the marble industry in the international arena under a comprehensive management approach consisting of three helices is a three-helix comprehensive management approach. In the light of this purpose, to synthesize research articles published in international research journals about the marble industry between 2014-2021; knowledge to help address issues in this mining sector; It has been necessary to propose the government-business-school approach

¹ Sustainability 2022, 14, 5576. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095576> <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability>
Sustainability 2022, 14, 5576 2 / 13 The problems in the marble industry in Mexico are as follows: Low It is characterized by productive performance, lack of management and organizational structures, high amount of raw material waste and negative social and environmental impacts in Comarca Lagunera, two representative marble use areas in Mexico (Mixteca Poblana)

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as a useful intervention guide for researchers to use when addressing issues in the marble industry value chain. The comprehensive triple helix intervention, also known as the triple helix intervention (THI), takes an inclusive approach to the sustainable development of the marble industry. This exploratory and descriptive research explores the socio-economic and environmental dynamics of the marble industry reported in scientific papers from 2014 to 2021, the forms of capital of the Mining, Mineral Sands and Sustainable Development (MMSD) project, namely natural capital, manufactured capital and social capital. explained with.

The technical, productive and environmental environment of the Mexican marble industry can be well described using this model, supported by various international research. Compared to other publications worldwide, the Mexican model is useful for describing the technical, productive and environmental background of the marble industry. These studies confirm aspects of marble extraction and processing processes reported by both international and national research works. Mining is one of the industrial activities that has a significant detrimental impact on ecosystems. More specifically, the mining industry handles the extraction and replacement of stone resources such as marble.

Italy, Spain, Portugal, Turkey and Greece are the five countries with the largest mineral reserves in the world. Turkey, Italy with 16% and Greece with 7% are the three main producers from these countries. Turkey has the highest share with 39%, followed by Italy. In this industry, Palestine, Turkey and Pakistan have identified problems, including the unsustainable management of waste from the extraction, recycling, transport and distribution of marble, and the demand for large volumes of water for cutting and processing . In addition, these countries have decided that large amounts of water are needed for cutting and polishing of marble cuts, and it is estimated that there will be a large demand for water for these processes. The high demand for this resource has a negative impact on the communities in which this industry operates as a result of the discharge of contaminated water. This water is characterized by a high content of 95% calcium carbonate and the remaining 5% contains chemicals such as calcium sulfide, chromium, zinc and iron used in cutting and finishing marble.

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On the other hand, the low quality of the facilities in terms of ventilation and lighting, which worsens the short and long-term health of the employees in this sector, is also a problem, as is the low level of professionalization of the employees in this sector. In this context, the lack of good practices in the management and operation of quarries, the absence of formally established environmental controls, companies with changing structures and organizations, negative externalities to public health and repulsive production systems are the factors affecting the integration of all these. (“Sustainability | Free Full-Text | A Triple-Helix Intervention Approach ...”) These factors can be divided into economic, social and environmental dimensions. In this context, it should be underlined that the lack of strategic alliances with suppliers and customers, the lack of communication and integration between areas, as well as the absence of marketing plans and inventory management ultimately affect the disarticulation of processes, which greatly affects the profitability of the company and increases negative externalities.

It has been reported that the marble and stone industry in Palestine, not so long ago, had negative effects on public health, the environment, water resources and ecosystems, as well as causing noise pollution in the regions and radical changes in the environmental landscape. Other adverse effects include depletion of water resources and degradation of ecosystems. The marble industry in Mexico has been experiencing a surge in economic activity since the 1960s. According to the 2019 statistical yearbook, Mexican Mining recorded a production of 1,964,041.14 tons with an estimated value of \$12 billion. This suggests that this sector of the economy fills a need that helps develop the nation's economy. However, it is necessary to take into account the negative externalities created by its extraction, transformation, storage and delivery. It has been observed that there is a disarticulation among the economic actors resulting in a repulsive production. This results in excessive waste of natural and human resources, which has a detrimental effect on economic, social, cultural and environmental factors. Meanwhile, it has been emphasized that the marble industry generates large amounts of waste from extraction to finishing, with waste disposal in open-air landfills, without a responsible final disposal. This is because the industry does not have a responsible final disposal for them. In 2020, the Mexican Ministry of Economy reported performance issues during the extraction and operation phase in terms of efficient use of resources,

low security levels, and efficient use of minerals. This is because the use of machinery continues in poor technological conditions alongside artisanal and improvised techniques.

In addition, performance problems were experienced in terms of effective use of minerals. For this reason, it has been determined that the smaller enterprises operating in this industrial zone are also behind the technological curve. The recommendations obtained as a result of the researches on this sector especially emphasize the need for an in-depth analysis and an action plan in order to eliminate the negative externalities of the marble sector and to make this sector a sustainable one. This recommendation was determined by research on this sector.

3. Market Expansion

The expansion of the market can largely be attributed to businesses reorganizing their operations and recovering from the impact of COVID-19. This impact has in the past led to restrictive containment measures such as social distancing, teleworking and business closures, all of which have resulted in operational difficulties. With a compound annual growth rate of 10.72%, the marble market share is estimated to reach 43.19 billion dollars in 2026. The growth in the construction industry is expected to increase the demand for marble in construction and decoration-related applications. All over the world, there has been an increase in the demand for residential accommodation. It is estimated that the world construction sector will reach a value of \$ 15.2 trillion by 2030, and the main drivers of this growth are countries such as India, China and the United States. Therefore, the expansion of the marble business will depend on the growth of the construction industry. The world marble market can be divided into: natural and synthetic according to its types; by shape, in sheet and powder form; by color, to white and others, and through application to sculptures and monuments, furniture and other uses. In 2021, the Asia-Pacific region had the largest share of the global marble market.

4. Marble Market Report of The Business Research Company

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The world marble market is expected to have the most growth in the Asia-Pacific region during the forecast period. Asia-Pacific, Western Europe, Eastern Europe, North America, South America, the Middle East and Africa are the areas covered by the study of the world marble market. Marble Global Market Report 2022 - Market Size, Trends and Global Forecast 2022-2026 is one of a series of new reports from The Business Research Company that forecasts the marble market overview, marble market analysis and market size and growth for the entire market. (“Global Marble Market Outlook, Opportunities And Strategies – Includes ...”) Market forecasts and analysis are created by a group of analysts and modelers with extensive professional experience and ability. According to research, the best countries and categories for opportunities and strategies are determined by market trends and tactics employed by major competitors.

It has locations around the world and employs specialist consultants in a wide variety of fields including manufacturing, healthcare, financial services, chemical manufacturing and technology. The most comprehensive database available anywhere in the world, The Business Research Company's core product is called the Global Market Model and is a market intelligence platform that covers a wide range of macroeconomic indicators and metrics. This platform covers 60 different geographical regions and 27 different industries. The Global Market Model takes into account datasets with several layers, which assists its users in assessing supply-demand gaps. In addition, the Marble Industry research study includes the future impact of the most important drivers and challenges, as well as supporting decision makers in the production of cost-effective professional choices. In addition, it discusses the size of the Marble market in many sub-sectors and factors contributing to its development, as well as growth trends, various investors, business leaders, dealers, vendors, Labor and media, and a SWOT analysis.

The 2022 Marble Market Report includes the following information and more:

- *Global Marble Market for United States, Canada, Mexico, Germany, France, United Kingdom, Russia, Italy, China, Japan, Korea,*
- *Full overview of country data and analysis,*
- *India, Southeast Asia, Australia, Brazil and Saudi Arabia, etc.,*

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- *In addition, it provides insight into the development of important regional marble markets such as those found in North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, South America and South America . Middle East and Africa. Identification and analysis of the potential of the marble market by type, deep dive, degradation, application capacity and end-use industry, impact assessment on the most important drivers and constraints as well as the dynamics of the worldwide marble market and current trends in the world.*

Marble Market segments provide assistance to decision makers in guiding their product, sales and marketing strategies. They also have the potential to accelerate your product development cycles by guiding the way you create product offerings for various segments.

- *The research looks at the industry's drivers and limits as well as its prospects.*
- *Recent trends and breakthroughs in the industry Competitive environment and tactics used by major players,*
- *Forecasts of the size and future of the market, both historical and present,*
- *Extensive research in the field of artificial intelligence,*
- *The Artificial Intelligence Chips Market report details everything from sales and prices to revenues and market share and growth rate.*

The research provides coverage of various sales channels, including distributors, traders and resellers. Primary sources include in-depth interviews with key opinion leaders and industry professionals (such as experienced frontline staff, managers, CEOs and marketing executives), as well as interviews with sub-distributors and end users. Research into the annual and financial reports of leading companies, public files, new journals, and other types of publications are examples of secondary sources.

This data includes consumption and income, as well as market share and growth rate.

5. Natural Marble

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Marble is a type of metamorphic rock typically made from recrystallized carbonate minerals such as calcite or dolomite. Limestone is the main component of marble. Marble is a material that is frequently used in sculpture as well as in the construction industry. Marble, in the form of crushed stone, is an aggregate used in the construction of building foundations, roads and railway beds. Both natural marble and artificial marble are considered primary marble categories. In its natural state, marble is a metamorphic stone made from calcite. This type of marble is known as "natural marble". The use of natural marble in construction materials, sculptures, exterior walls of houses, kitchen counters, stairs and other applications is common. The term "artificial marble" refers to synthetic marble produced by combining small pieces of natural marble with stone powder, plastic, cement and sand. Artificial marble comes in a wide range of colors and designs, making it a popular choice for use as a building material in a variety of settings, including home exteriors, kitchens, walls and floors. The market can be divided into two different forms:

- *Slab and Powder.*

Marble slabs are quarried and then resized before being sold. The processing of marble results in the formation of marble dust. ("Health Risk Assessment of Marble Dust at Marble Workshops - ResearchGate") It can be incorporated into cement or fine aggregates as a filler in the concrete making process. The market can be divided into white and other categories by color. In addition to its high purity, pure white marble has excellent grounding and relaxing metaphysical properties. White marble is a popular choice for a variety of applications, including flooring, construction, interior design and art. The decoration of buildings, statues and monuments, furniture and various other uses are important applications of marble. The global market size of the marble industry, regional shares, competitors with marble share, detailed marble segments, market trends and opportunities, and all the additional data you may need to develop in the marble industry are included in the marble research report.

The marble market study examines the following geographical areas: Asia-Pacific region, Western Europe, Eastern Europe, North America, South America, Middle East and Africa. The scope of the marble market research includes the countries of Australia, Brazil, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Japan, Russia, South Korea, the United Kingdom and the United States.

The world-scale marble market can be grouped as follows:

- 1) By type: natural and synthetic
- 2) By Form: Flooring, Powder
- 3) Classified by Color: White, Other
- 4) Usage: Architecture and Decoration, Statues and Monuments, Furniture and Other Applications

6. Marble Mining

The term "marble" refers to a precious decorative stone that has been used by man since the beginning of written history. It is possible to argue that the marble mining and processing industries are among the oldest on the entire planet. Several types of marble, such as granite and alabaster, are the two types of fine stones most used by the Ancient Egyptians about 5,000 years ago. They were familiar with forty different ornamental stones. Some historians are of the opinion that it was the Ancient Egyptians who taught the Greeks and Romans to extract and prepare marble. Marble has been the main driver of economic activity for over a millennium in a city like Carrara in Italy, and the city's prosperity is largely dependent on and focused on commodities. Marble has now become a separate commodity traded around the world. The price and value of marble are determined on the one hand by the natural characteristics of the marble (such as quality, type and color) and on the other hand by the technical processes applied to the marble (by giving it a special quality). As a result, it can be seen that the manufacture of marble is both highly specialized and very dependent on the amount of technology used. In order for a nation to dominate this sector, this precious stone must not only be abundant in its natural wealth, but also have a strong technological infrastructure that enables it to extract and process marble in accordance with local production. Only then will the nation be able to claim the position of industry leader. As little information has been published on the Egyptian marble industry in general, a substantial amount of field research has been conducted and in-depth interviews have been conducted with business owners, geologists as well as with the industry. Then, the representative companies were examined according to the following criteria. It was established to represent the generation of marble

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producers that developed after the 1980s and shaped this industrial sector in the last two decades. The existence of large undiscovered marble deposits in Egypt has been confirmed by experts. In addition, the commercial name of the removed marble, which may or may not be the same as the scientific definition, is also mentioned. A good example of this kind of inconsistency is the term "Black Carrara". Carrara marble is among the most well-known varieties of Italian marble found all over the world. The term "Egyptian marble" indicates that this type of marble from Egypt, although black in color, is comparable to Carrara marble from Italy. It is important to note that the color of Carrara is white by default.

On the supply side, quantity competition occurs; this means that suppliers who can deliver scale quantities and/or manage their own quarries have a clear competitive advantage over those who cannot. However, there is intense competition on price. Sometimes smaller suppliers have emptied the market by drastically lowering their rates to generate more revenue for themselves. Quality makes an important contribution to the differentiation of products in the market (vertical differentiation). It depends on the targeted demand, the location of the end customer and whether production is for export. In addition, there is the possibility of horizontal differentiation (according to the type and color of the marble produced). Although demand almost always fluctuates throughout the year, the marble industry is heavily dependent on the economic cycle of the construction industry, albeit belatedly. There are several implicit barriers to admission, including:

- (1) Lack of skilled workers as there are no colleges or schools for skilled workers to work in this sector,*
- (2) Relatively cheap imports mainly from Asia,*
- (3) The size of the firm, as the industry occupies a lot of space and preferably not less than 5,000 m², which is suitable for a marble processing unit,*
- (4) Since the industry is characterized by a regional concentration of factories, location and*
- (5) Lack of currency or foreign exchange for purchasing raw materials.*

Polishing can be carried out using fully automatic equipment, semi-automatic equipment or manual machinery, among other processes. Generally, technologies are purchased from countries in Europe, including Italy, Germany, Spain, India or Turkey. There are also some Egyptian

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machines produced in workshops that copy the patent design of some of the imported machines. Some of these machines are imported from other countries. Although these machines are capable of performing the required function, they are relatively inefficient and produce a product that is not standardized and does not conform to generally accepted international standards. Diamond blades for cutting hard stones are an essential component of technical progress. Diamond blades wear out fairly quickly, usually within three months of use, resulting in a significant increase in the semi-fixed costs of the mill owners.

growth in marble demand that has made its exploitation, extraction and conversion into other forms a model for successful economic development on an international scale . However, this sector has reported a detrimental impact on the environment created by low productivity levels, high levels of raw material waste and the procedures it uses to remove and replace dimension stone. An analysis of the environmental, social and cultural aspects of the industry from the perspective of their sustainability potential has been presented over the last decade. The findings show the production of pollutants, their discharge into water bodies, dust emission from cutting operations, the presence of occupational hazards, the development of environmental noise and damage to health in Palestine.

Similar situations have been reported in the marble industry in Turkey, corrective actions have been proposed in the marble industry to reduce the damage to workers' health and the environment as well as to strengthen the economic aspects. As a result of these actions, the productivity of the marble process has improved by 7%. In this context, it is proposed to develop a method that lays the groundwork for establishing a cleaner production scheme for the assessment of air, soil and water pollution problems resulting from stone and marble activities in China. These problems arise from activities. Over the last half century, there has been a profound shift in the fundamental concepts that underpin free market competition, as well as the product manufacturing and service sectors. As a result of these changes, the world has essentially become a single market and the standard that businesses must comply with in order to survive in the current market conditions is to provide high quality goods and / or services. On the other hand, any serious effort to improve quality must take into account the costs incurred in doing so. This is because the goal of continuous improvement programs is not just to meet customers' expectations, but to do so at the lowest

possible cost. This can only be achieved by reducing the costs necessary to achieve quality, and the reduction of these costs can only be achieved if they are first recognized and then quantified. In other words, it's the only way for this to happen. It is necessary to apply cost management over quality in order to satisfy consumers and keep expenditures under control. As a result, taking and reporting COQ measurements should be seen as an important issue for management (Schiffauerova and Thomson, 2006).

Marble production is based on the use of non-renewable natural resources as input. Traditional quality control (QC) approaches to marble work are difficult to implement due to the many challenges nature brings. On the other hand, quality control and efficiency are very important aspects of mining as they have the potential to slow the depletion of natural resources. Raw natural stone blocks, which have been geologically developed in nature over millions of years, are the inputs for the marble system. It is almost difficult to practically control all the qualities that directly affect the standards and to keep the quality at a high level in this sector. The only choice that can be made is to meticulously select the most desirable building blocks at the beginning of the process and keep them under tight control throughout the process. And as a result of these challenges, categorizing and calculating quality-related expenses in the natural stone business is a very difficult endeavor that rarely happens.

7. Definition of the Term "Quality"

Although the primary definition of the term "quality" is customer satisfaction achieved through a product or service, Campanella and Corcoran (1983) and Paul (1990) have defined quality costs from the zero-defect approach as the difference between actual costs. According to Juran and Gryna (1993), the definition of quality is "fitness for purpose", while according to Crosby (1979), the definition of quality is "conformity to requirements". Deming (1986) argues that quality is achieved when there is consistency with the right purpose. According to Crosby (1983), quality costs are defined as nonconformity costs. According to Szymanski (1985), quality cost analysis is a technique that reveals patterns to management so that they can take proper action. The COQ approach and several QC models focus on the principle of measuring and compiling quality-related

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costs as its central focus. Many scholars have proposed a wide variety of methods for analyzing the relationships between quality and cost (Hollocker, 1986; Dahlgaard et al., 1992; Asher, 1987; Gibson et al., 1991; Morse, 1993). Whitehall (1986) and Brennan et al. (1990) found quality cost factors using flowcharts and structured interviews, respectively. A goal programming model was set up by Schniederjans and Karuppan (1995) to help select the most proper set of quality control instruments, the first step in designing a quality control system. According to Desai (2008), although there are many articles and books that address quality cost collection, they do not supply much help and direction on how to set up a cost collection technique. The PAF model is the earliest of all the QC models (1957) created by Feigenbaum (1956) and Masser. Quality cost models have been used to find and segment expenses and to aid accounting systems in accurately recording quality-related costs. Although there are four groups of quality cost models (PAF model, opportunity cost model, process cost model, and activity-based cost model), the PAF classification is the basis of most quality cost models (Plunket and Dale, 1987). "; Machowski and Dale, 1998; Sandoval-Chávez and Beruvides, 1998; Hwang and Aspinwal, 1996; Desai, 2008)." ("Cost of quality management: An empirical study from Turkish marble industry") The PAF model is one of the best-known quality cost models among quality practitioners. It has found use in both the manufacturing and service industries and is built on the principle of classifying quality costs into three basic categories: prevention, assessment and failure costs.

Abed and Dale (1987) said that failure costs can be divided into two subclasses, internal and external failure costs, in addition to these three categories. In addition, they discovered that the components of quality expenses can simply be broken down into the categories of prevention, evaluation, and internal and external failure costs across all businesses. Costs associated with prevention are costs incurred when steps are taken to ensure that a process produces high-quality goods and services. Failure costs are spent on restoring quality in goods and services before (internal) or after (external) delivery to the customer. Evaluation costs are related to the evaluation of the degree of quality achieved by the process (Schiffauerova and Thomson, 2006). The PAF method is useful for analyzing business operations processes, accounting systems, and monthly departmental reports to identify the different cost elements associated with each of the four cost categories (Sharma et al., 2007).

8. Natural Stone Products Exported from Turkey

The United States was the largest target country for natural stone products exported from Turkey in 2017, accounting for more than 31% of Turkey's total exports. It should come as no surprise that any adjustment to the Generalized System of Preferences would have a major impact on the overall exports of finished natural stone products made in Turkey at a time when the country's economy is struggling to recover from serious difficulties. However, the marble industry in Turkey, which is the world's largest exporting country, has the capacity to overcome any problem that may develop. Turkey is currently in the first place. World-renowned marble from Turkey, marble production in Turkey is promoting all over the world; but the country also has abundant natural reserves of a wide variety of minerals, rocks and stones. Turkey 's reserves are not only remarkable for their quantity, but also for the quality of what they contain.

Turkish marble is a metamorphic rock composed primarily of recrystallized carbonate minerals such as calcite and dolomite. May have marble formations. Stone masons use the term "marble" to refer to both metamorphosed and unmetamorphized limestone. Geologists use the word "marble" to refer to metamorphosed limestone; however, masons use the term "marble" to refer to both metamorphosed and non-metamorphized limestone. Turkey's natural stone industry primarily produces marble, granite, limestone, travertine, serpentine, diabase and slate. The General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration of Turkey (General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration, MTA) estimated the natural stone resources as 5×10^9 cubic meters in 1996 for the first time. Since then, Turkey's natural stone sector has been growing steadily from year to year. Its average annual growth rate has doubled that of the rest of the world. Turkey ranks fourth in the world in terms of natural stone production after China, India and Italy.

Although Turkey's marble reserves are concentrated in Afyon, Balıkesir, Denizli, Tokat, Muğla and Çanakkale, they are scattered throughout the country. More than 680 million mt of marble, known as Gölpazarı Beige, found southeast of Istanbul, makes it Turkey's most valuable resource of its kind. Similarly, Mustafa Kemalpaşa, found in the southwest of Istanbul, has approximately 190 million mt of white marble. Marmara Region, Sivrihisar in Eskişehir; Harmantepe, Dokurcun

and Akyaz in Sakarya, Hamursuztaşı in Muğla; Aksihar, Yalova, Göksun in Kahramanmaraş, Kazdağı in Edremit; Harmantepe, Dokurcun and Akyaz in Sakarya, and Hamursu are rich in marble.

Turkey has many marble deposits due to its location in the Alpine-Himalayan belt. More than 250 types of marbles in assorted colors and patterns have been produced from these beds, and 100 of them are known worldwide.

9. Iscehisar and Known Marble Types

Iscehisar is such a known type of marble. Afyon-Iscehisar is of Paleozoic age and has been quarried since the Roman Empire period. Afyon region is known as one of the most important marble production and processing centers in Turkey. Afyon province, which has 3.5% of Turkey's operable marble reserves (3,872.000.000 tons), realizes 9% of the total block marble production. "409 marble processing plants in Afyon produce 19% of the total slab in Turkey." ("Geological and technical characterization of Iscehisar (Afyon-Turkey ...)") As a result of marble production activities, approximately 340,000 tons of marble waste has accumulated in the region. While some of these unformed marble blocks are reused and reclaimed, most are thrown away. There are two waste marble storage areas in the Afyon-Iscehisar region. All the solid and fine-grained marble wastes are stored in the waste marble storage areas in Susuz Boğazı and in the nearby Iscehisar marble quarries. The ecological effects of marble waste, which once spilled everywhere and showed visual pollution, are now minimized. Many monuments and structures were built using marble in ancient times. Especially during the Roman Empire, the use of marble increased. Important public buildings needed the finest marble, and high-quality stones were often used in imperial building projects. For this purpose, many marble quarries were opened in the imperial lands and the old ones were reused. Any type of rock that can be cut and polished in a commercially suitable block size is defined as marble. Iscehisar marble quarry is one of the largest and oldest quarries in Turkey. In the Roman period, the marbles extracted from the quarry were sent to the coastal Aegean and Mediterranean cities as processed marbles or blocks by river and sea. For this reason, many marble monuments and artifacts made of Iscehisar marble can be seen in ancient

cities of Turkey and Europe and today in museums (İleri et al. 2001). In the later stages of the operation of the Dokimeion quarries, in the 3rd century AD, large numbers of white marble and violet (pavonazetto) marble blocks, semi- or fully worked marbles and works of art were sent to Rome (Fant, 1993; Sodini, 2002). These marbles were used in various parts of Anatolia such as Ephesus, Bergama and Hierapolis, as well as meeting the local marble needs, and were also exported to Europe and North Africa (Albustanlıoğlu, 2001). The first assessments of natural stone reserve estimates in Turkey, found on the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic belt, where the richest marble deposits are found, were made by the General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration (MTA, Ankara, Turkey) 5.1 billion m³ (13.9 billion) in 1966. tons) has been declared a potential marble reserve. Approximately 40% of the world's marble reserves are in Turkey (Onrgan et al. 2006). Iscehisar is such a known type of marble. Iscehisar is of Paleozoic age and has been quarried since the Roman Empire period. "Afyon region is known as one of the most important marble production and processing centers in Turkey." ("marble processing machines turkey") Afyon province, which has 3.5% of Turkey's operable marble reserves (3,872.000.000 tons), realizes 9% of the total block marble production. "409 marble processing plants in Afyon produce 19% of the total slab in Turkey." ("Geological and technical characterization of Iscehisar (Afyon-Turkey ...)") As a result of marble production activities, approximately 340,000 tons of marble waste has accumulated in the region. While some of these unformed marble blocks are reused and reclaimed, most are thrown away. There are two waste marble storage areas in Iscehisar region. All the solid and fine-grained marble wastes are stored in the waste marble storage areas in Susuz Boğazı and in the nearby Iscehisar marble quarries. The ecological effects of marble waste, which once spilled everywhere and showed visual pollution, are now minimized. Today's meaning of marble includes all kinds of natural stones with high decorative features in the stone industry. Practically it is a mono-mineral rock composed mainly of calcite and/or dolomite. Pure marbles having more than 95% calcite are usually white. It may have lesser amounts of quartz, feldspar, mica, chlorite and other minerals (Mrozek-Wysocka 2014). Turkey has many large complex crystal structures found in assorted colors of marble. The extraction of these marbles from the quarry dates to ancient times. In ancient times almost all-important statues, monumental, religious and important buildings were made of marble, so in ancient times only marble trade was

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common. Besides marble, many natural stones (limestone, travertine and sandstone) have been mined, but most have only been used locally (Herz 1988).

Afyon marble quarries have attracted the attention of many researchers because traces of ancient stone cuts from the Roman period can still be seen and there are many semi-processed artifacts. (“Abstract - assets.researchsquare.com”) After the first studies started in the 1920s, studies were conducted on semi-finished architectural pieces and sculpture materials and various works (commonly sculptures and sarcophagi) made from these marbles in the Dokimeion marble quarries (Waelkens 1985). A lot of research has been done about Dokimeion white marble and this number is increasing. Some of these studies are related to marble quarrying and quarrying in ancient times. Albustanlıoğlu (2002) and Fant (1989) investigated the operation and export organization of Dokimeion marble quarries during the Roman period. Many of the scientific studies conducted in Iscehisar marble quarries include topics such as the economy of marble, environmental problems, and the evaluation of marble waste. Çelik and Sabah (2008) investigated the geological and technical characterization of Iscehisar marble deposits and the effect of marble waste on environmental pollution. (“Abstract - assets.researchsquare.com”) There are many architectural works, sarcophagi and sculptures showed in museums in Anatolia and many Mediterranean countries. Many researchers have examined the works made of Iscehisar marble, which are showed in museums in Mediterranean countries . Researchers examined abandoned marble blocks and semi-worked artifacts in the Iscehisar marble quarries. Fant (1985) reported that four unfinished sarcophagus lids made of fine-grained white marble were found in the Docimium quarry in Iscehisar. Fant (1988a) said that there were two sculptures and some architectural works in the Docimium quarry in Iscehisar. Many researchers have studied the physico-mechanical properties of Turkish natural building stones, including Afyon white marbles . Özgüven and Özçelik (2014) examined the physico-mechanical properties of some Turkish natural building blocks. Çelik and Sert (2020b) investigated the importance of Afyonviolet (Pavonazetto) marble from the Roman era to the present and the evaluation of its durability with aging tests. For this reason, many marble monuments and works of art made of Iscehisar-Afyon marble are showed in ancient cities in Turkey and Europe and in museums today (I leri et al. 2001). This has been well known for 2300 years. More than 400 marble processing plants in the region use at least one gang saw or an S/T

(disc cutter). The slab production in these facilities in 2000 was 6.611.000 m², which is approximately 25% of the total slab production in Turkey (Kuscu et al. 2001). These figures emphasize the importance of Iscehisar-Afyon marble products in the Turkish marble industry. Geology of Iscehisar-Afyon region There are two Iscehisar-Afyon marble deposits in Iscehisar district on the Ankara highway, 25 km northeast of Afyon. ("Geological and technical characterization of Iscehisar (Afyon-Turkey ...")

These rocks, which are generally of sedimentary origin, completed their metamorphic evolution in the pre-Mesozoic era (Tolluoglu et al., 1997). Afyon metamorphites are generally brown and green in color, with a highly folded albite-chlorite-muscovite-biotite-quartz schist at the base. In these schists, metaconglomerate marble and calcschist are seen as large lenses and belts. The schist thickness is estimated to be 2000 m and the upper contact is unconformable with Tertiary units (Metin et al., et al., 1987).

10. Conclusion

Iscehisar marbles were known as "Synnada marbles" (currently Suhut) by the Romans in the world, and "Dokimeion marbles" in Anatolia (Gönç-er, 1971). In the later stages of the operation of the Dokimeion quarries (235-236 BC), large numbers of white marble blocks and semi- or fully-worked marble works of art were left in the rubble. The most interesting of these figures are human figures (Sodini, 2002). In 2000, 110.350 m³ of block marble and 650,000 m³ of crushed marble were mined in Iscehisar-Afyon. In the same period, Turkey's total block marble production is 1,100,000 m³. Approximately 9% of block marble production was realized in Iscehisar-Afyon. Based on this information and the main topic of our article, Iscehisar marbles need more promotion, more investment and the attention it deserves. The fact that these reserves and values are presented to the world as they deserve by being processed with concepts such as "mineral and marble, natural stones museum" requires not being limited to only one production and export concepts. It is obvious that the promotion, which is our suggestion, will also contribute in the sense of "tourism" by giving the right to a cultural value.

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